

An Algorithm for Making Informed Decisions about Patient Care from Interactions between Genetic and Environmental Factors

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Abstract

The use of statistics in medicine is important for making informed decisions for patient care and discovering possible new treatments or cures. Thus, it is often useful to find what factors lead to increased risk of disease. In statistics, the association of one factor with outcome, may differ in the presence of another factor. This interaction, if not addressed, may cause the association with the outcome to go undetected. Interactions are often difficult to distinguish with traditional methods because of the need to state the possible interactions *a priori*. If there are a large number of factors, the possible interactions quickly become infeasible to enumerate. Decision trees such as CART eliminate the need to state the interactions *a priori* and is often used to identify interactions associated with outcome. CART, however, tends to be biased toward the inclusion of continuous factors over binary ones such as those found in genetic data. This paper proposes a method called C.Logic that eliminates the need to state interactions *a priori* and can effectively identify which interactions are associated with outcome without being biased toward the inclusion of continuous factors into the model.

1 Introduction

Researchers are often interested in investigating genetic variants that are associated with disease outcome. With the completion of the Human Genome Project and the International HapMap, along with many technological advancements in gene mapping, researchers are able to perform genome-wide association studies (GWAS). GWAS involves analyzing whole samples of genomes to look for genetic variations associated with disease. In a GWA study, it is common practice to gather DNA samples from both cases and controls and scan for genetic variations, or Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs). SNPs that are more frequently found in cases than controls are studied further. Though GWA studies have found many common variants associated with diseases such as in Celiac's Disease and Crohn's Disease [1] among others, these variants typically explain only a fraction of the inherited contribution or heritability of disease risk. [2]

It is possible, however, that certain SNPs are associated with disease outcome only in the presence of other factors. These possible interactions will go undiscovered if variables are eliminated based solely main effect or if genetic factors are not considered in connection with environmental factors. These interactions could explain at least a portion of the remaining variance in disease outcome.

Neglect of possible gene-by-environment interactions in GWA studies has led to the emergence of specifically designed gene-by-environment experiments in order to find missing heritability [3]. In these randomized controlled experiments, the environment is manipulated in standard ways. For example, in studying dopamine receptor D4 (DRD4) gene, researchers noticed that toddlers who carried this allele showed reduced destructive behavior after a parenting class was administered versus toddlers who did not carry this allele [4, 3]. Another way to explain missing heritability or variance could be to identify these interactions with statistical methods.

However, identifying interactions that lead to increased risk of disease may be difficult with traditional statistical methods. This difficulty is due, in part, to the fact that in many statistical methods, interactions must be identified *a priori* in order to be studied. If all interactions are included in a model, it quickly becomes computationally prohibitive.

Decision trees eliminate the need to specifically state interactions *a priori* and instead can search all possible interactions over a large sample space. Classification and Regression Trees (CART), a common decision tree method,

can identify interactions to model outcome but it is biased toward the inclusion of continuous variables as opposed to binary genetic data[5]. Logic regression is an alternative tree-based method specifically designed to find interactions in genetic data, but it was not designed for continuous variables [6]. Continuous variables must be dichotomized before use in the model.

This paper suggests an alternative algorithm for identifying continuous and binary interactions associated with disease. Section 2 of this paper will explore current methods for interaction identification as well as propose an alternative method. Section 3 will discuss a simulation designed to explore how this new methodology compares to current practices while section 4 will present the results. Section 5 will provide a discussion and review of the topics present as well as make recommendations for use of new methodology.

2 Methods

2.1 Current Methods

Logistic Regression is a traditional statistical approach often used to model dichotomous outcome from continuous and binary data. When investigating interactions, however, they must be added to the model *a priori*. When there are a small number of variables, all possible combinations of the variables can be included in the model without difficulty. For example, if there are 4 main effects, the number of total terms to include in the model would be $2^4 - 1 = 15$. If the number of variables increases to 20, however, the number of model terms becomes $2^{20} - 1 = 1,048,575$ which would be computationally prohibitive. Also, if the number of parameters exceeds the number of observations, which is common in genetic data, then logistic regression will fail.

In Machine Learning techniques there is no need to identify interactions *a priori*. These techniques involve algorithms that search through an entire data space to find patterns that can predict outcome. Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) is a machine learning technique that can model complex data, but its models result in a "Black Box" effect which is difficult to interpret. Another machine learning technique, Support Vector Machines (SVMs) classifies disease outcome. Like, ANN the results often lack interpretability. Also, if the number of variables exceeds the number of samples, the method will fail.

Decision Tree methods are an efficient way to identify possible interactions in the data that are associated with increased risk of disease. The resulting models are interpretable and the method can handle high dimensionality. CART, a common decision tree method, uses recursive partitioning to create homogeneous rectangular subsets in the data. As seen in Figure 1, the first split occurs at the parent node, N_{parent} , where the data space is divided into two regions N_{left} and N_{right} . CART models response by majority vote meaning that if more observations in N_{right} are characterized by $Y = 1$, then the entire region is labeled as 1, or disease positive. Next, one or both of the regions are divided again and a vote is taken. This continues until some stopping rule is applied.

Figure 1: CART Splitting

As stated earlier, CART is biased toward the inclusion of continuous variables meaning that if it has a choice of including a continuous variable or a binary variable into the model, it will choose the continuous [5]. Also, by design, CART is inflexible. Once a split is made on a variable, a branch is formed and certain combinations of variables are no longer viable.

Logic regression is an alternative tree based method that uses Boolean logic to model a binary outcome. It is this use of Boolean logic that makes logic regression inherently more flexible than CART. For example, consider

the logic statement $D = 1 : (X_1 \text{ and } X_2) \text{ or } (X_1 \text{ and } X_3)$. As shown in figure 2, this can be modeled exactly with logic regression but not with CART.

Figure 2: CART Splitting

2.2 Methodology of C.Logic

LR, however, is not designed for the inclusion of continuous variables. The splits that CART creates during its implementation must be done prior to implementation for LR. An important question, therefore, is the best way to make these dichotomizations while preserving the integrity of the data. This involves not dichotomizing interacting variables independent of each other. Thus, using simultaneous dichotomization [7]

2.3 Simultaneous Dichotomization

What follows is a brief description of simultaneous dichotomization as developed by Prince Nelson et al. [7]. Consider the possibility of two variables,

X_1 and X_2 with the following relationship with outcome:

$$P_{Y=1} = P_{(X_1 \geq T_1, X_2 \geq T_2)} P_{Y|(X_1 \geq T_1, X_2 \geq T_2)} + P_{(X_1 < T_1 \text{ OR } X_2 < T_2)} P_{Y|(X_1 < T_1 \text{ OR } X_2 < T_2)} \quad (1)$$

where

$$P_{(X_1 < T_1 \text{ OR } X_2 < T_2)} = P_{(X_1 \geq T_1, X_2 < T_2)} + P_{(X_1 < T_1, X_2 \geq T_2)} + P_{(X_1 < T_1, X_2 < T_2)}$$

and

$$P_{Y=1|X_1 < T_1 \text{ OR } X_2 < T_2} = P_{Y|(P_{(X_1 \geq T_1, X_2 < T_2)} + P_{(X_1 < T_1, X_2 \geq T_2)} + P_{(X_1 < T_1, X_2 < T_2)})}$$

The probabilities corresponding to a 2×2 contingency table for the joint condition of $(X_1 \geq T_1, X_2 \geq T_2)$ and $Y = 1$ or 0 are summarized in Table 1. Here, Y is associated with X_1 and X_2 through an interaction, and thus $P_{Y=1}$ is larger when the interaction is present. If Y is associated with \mathbf{X} through an interaction, then $P_{Y=1}$ is larger when in the presence of the interaction. For this paper, an interaction between two or more variables means that there is an increased risk of $P_{Y=1}$ when both or all variables are present.

	$Y = 1$	$Y = 0$	
$X_1 \geq T_1, X_2 \geq T_2$	$a_J = P(Y = 1, X_1 \geq T_1, X_2 \geq T_2)$ $= P_{X_1 \geq T_1, X_2 \geq T_2} P_{Y X_1 \geq T_1, X_2 \geq T_2}$	$b_J = P(Y = 0, X_1 \geq T_1, X_2 \geq T_2)$ $= P_{X_1 \geq T_1, X_2 \geq T_2}$ $- P_{X_1 \geq T_1, X_2 \geq T_2} P_{Y X_1 \geq T_1, X_2 \geq T_2}$	$P_{X_1 \geq T_1, X_2 \geq T_2}$
$X_1 < T_1 \vee X_2 < T_2$	$c_J = P(Y = 1, X_1 < T_1, X_2 \geq T_2)$ $+ P(Y = 1, X_1 \geq T_1, X_2 < T_2)$ $+ P(Y = 1, X_1 < T_1, X_2 < T_2)$ $= (P_{X_1 < T_1, X_2 \geq T_2}$ $+ P_{X_1 \geq T_1, X_2 < T_2}$ $+ P_{X_1 < T_1, X_2 < T_2}) P_{Y X_1 < T_1 \vee X_2 < T_2}$	$d_J = P(Y = 0, X_1 < T_1, X_2 \geq T_2)$ $+ P(Y = 0, X_1 \geq T_1, X_2 < T_2)$ $+ P(Y = 0, X_1 < T_1, X_2 < T_2)$ $= (P_{X_1 < T_1, X_2 \geq T_2}$ $+ P_{X_1 \geq T_1, X_2 < T_2}$ $+ P_{X_1 < T_1, X_2 < T_2})$ $- (P_{X_1 < T_1, X_2 \geq T_2}$ $+ P_{X_1 \geq T_1, X_2 < T_2}$ $+ P_{X_1 < T_1, X_2 < T_2}) P_{Y=0 X_1 < T_1 \vee X_2 < T_2}$	$P_{X_1 > T_1, X_2 < T_2}$ $+ P_{X_1 < T_1, X_2 \geq T_2}$ $+ P_{X_1 < T_1, X_2 < T_2}$
	$P_{Y=1}$	$P_{Y=0}$	

Table 1: The 2x2 contingency table for continuous variables X_1 and X_2 and dichotomous outcome Y where X_1 and X_2 are jointly thresholded at T_1 and T_2 respectively

2.4 C.Logic Algorithm

Algorithm for C.Logic

1. Take t bootstrap samples of the data
2. For each continuous variables, X , in each sample order the values to create a variable oX
3. For each continuous variable in each sample calculate the cell counts for a 2×2 contingency table as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} a_k &= \sum_{k=1}^t I(X_k \geq oX_k) \wedge I(Y_k = 1) \\ b_k &= \sum_{k=1}^t I(X_k \geq oX_k) \wedge I(Y_k = 0) \\ c_k &= \sum_{k=1}^t I(X_k < oX_k) \wedge I(Y_k = 1) \\ d_k &= \sum_{k=1}^t I(X_k < oX_k) \wedge I(Y_k = 0) \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

4. At each value of X_t , use the corresponding contingency table to calculate the six statistics found in Table 2
5. Find the maximum value for each statistic for each variable in each bootstrap sample.
6. For each continuous variable, find the median of the bootstrap samples. These medians are the new thresholds.
7. Dichotomize the continuous variables of the original data set with the new thresholds.
8. Apply logic regression

Odds Ratio	Youden's Statistic	Chi-Square
$\frac{ad}{bc}$	$\frac{a}{a+c} + \frac{d}{b+d} - 1$	$\frac{(ad-bc)^2}{(a+b)(c+d)(b+d)(a+c)}$
Kappa Statistic	Relative Risk*	Gini Index
$\frac{(a+d)-((a+b)(a+c)+(c+d)(b+d))}{1-((a+b)(a+c)+(c+d)(b+d))}$	$\frac{a/(a+b)}{c/(c+d)}$	$(P_y(1 - P_y)) - (\frac{ab}{a+b} + \frac{cd}{c+d})$

Table 2: Formulas for statistics for selecting a threshold for a continuous variable X to discriminate a binary outcome Y based on the probabilities in Table *For cohort study designs only

3 Simulation Study

In section 2 we developed an algorithm, C.Logic, for extending logic regression to include continuous variables. In this section, we compare C.Logic to CART in order to investigate which method performs better in identifying interactions that are associated with the outcome.

To compare C.Logic to CART, we first generate a data set as follows:

1. Two binary variables, X_1 and X_2 , generated under a binomial distribution with probability of 0.3
2. A binary and continuous, X_3 and X_4 , variable generated under a multivariate distribution such that $\mathbf{X} \sim N_2(\mathbf{0}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \rho \\ \rho & 1 \end{pmatrix})$, where $\rho = 0$
3. Two continuous variables, X_5 and X_6 , generated under a multivariate distribution such that $\mathbf{X} \sim N_2(\mathbf{0}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \rho \\ \rho & 1 \end{pmatrix})$, where $\rho = 0$
4. Set true thresholds for continuous variables T_{x_4} , T_{x_5} , and T_{x_6} , as the inverse normal value of 0.3, 0.524.
5. Generate an outcome variable Y so that $Y = 1$ when $X_1 = X_2 = 1$ or $X_3 = 1$ and $X_4 \geq T_{x_4}$ or $X_5 \geq T_{x_5}$ and $X_6 \geq t_{x_6}$ with $P_{Y|T}$ such that $P_{Y|T} > P_{Y|F}$
6. Generate 11 binary and 3 continuous noise variables.

For our simulation, we use sample sizes of 300, 500, 1000, 1500, and 2000. We also consider odds ratios of 2, 4, and 8. Each simulation is run with 500 repetitions using a bootstrap of 10 per sample.

4 Simulation Results

Figure 3: Simulation results showing sample size by the proportion of times the interactions are identified under the case-control study design comparing C.Logic to CART

Figure 3 shows the results from a cohort study design scenario. Each plot shows the sample size by the proportion of times the interaction is correctly identified exactly. The columns in the figure show the interactions: $X_1 X_2$, $X_3 X_4$, and $X_5 X_6$, as described in section 3. The rows show the impact of increasing the strength of association with Y , represented by the odds ratio in the data. For each interaction, as the sample size increases both C.Logic and

CART improve in identifying the interactions. As the odds ratio increases so does the proportion of times the interactions are exactly identified in a C.Logic or CART tree. Both methods perform poorly when identifying the X_5X_6 interaction when the odds ratio is 2. As the odds ratio increases to 8, however, C.Logic improves and performs better than CART with C.Logic identifying the correct interactions 75% of the time compared to 37% with CART. C.Logic outperforms CART by the greatest margin for the X_1X_2 interaction when odds ratio is 8.

5 Conclusion

Identifying interactions that lead to increased risk of disease is an important problem in both medicine and statistics. If a factor increases risk of disease only in the presence of another factor, it may go undiscovered with traditional statistical methods. CART is a tree-based method that can identify interactions to model a binary outcome. Studies have shown, however, that CART can be biased toward the inclusion of continuous variables[5]. Logic regression is specifically designed to find binary interactions that are associated with a binary outcome.

In this paper, we created a new algorithm, C.Logic, that allows for the inclusion of continuous variables in a logic regression framework. Simulation results show that C.Logic is superior to CART in identifying interactions of variables associated with outcome an improves as odds ratio increases.

One limitation of this paper is that the data was simulated under the assumption of Equation 1. This implies that only an interaction between factors leads to increased risk of disease. Data that does not follow this framework could have less than optimal results. Yet, Prince et. al showed in their research that even when there are no interactions in the data, simultaneous dichotomization, which is used in the C.Logic algorithm still determines more accurate cutpoints indicating that this algorithm will perform well in many types of data sets.

5.1 Bibliography

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